

Adaptive Lidar Systems for Wind Turbine Control

Data Collection

What data will you collect or create?

In terms of classification, in this Ph.D. project, the data could be classified into three main types:

1. Source codes that are written in certain programming languages such as MATLAB, Python, C++, and Fortran. This type of data is used during the Ph.D. project to perform the following procedures: pre-processing, analysis, numerical simulation, and post-processing to other types of data (2 and 3).
2. Measurement data from lidar devices, anemometers, wind turbines, and oscilloscopes. This type of data needs to be stored with a certain platform and usually stored in the original format when it is collected.
3. Simulated data that could be generated by source code. This type of data is not necessary to be stored, since it is reproducible by executing the type 1 codes. So only the setup of the scripts will be published.
4. Non-open source data such as Dynamic-link library files, this type of data is only shared among licensed partners in non-open form.

In addition to the three types listed above, there will be documentation of the data or metadata, which will be discussed later.

The collect or created data will mainly focus on the following topics:

- **Measurement of mast tower:** For type 2 data, we will use the data measured from available anemometers. For type 3 data, the turbulence will be simulated either by the spectral based approach using Turbsim, Mann turbulence generator, and in-house written code or by the Computational Fluid Mechanics (CFD) based approach using OpenFOAM.
- **Lidar Measurement:** For some studies where measured data is not feasible, the lidar measurement is simulated by in-house written codes or by public available codes by other authors. In addition, the lidar simulated data is usually used together with the turbulence data.
- **Turbine Measurement:** The turbine measurement data can be collected by sensors configured on a research turbine. Or it can be simulated by an aeroelastic simulation tool such as OpenFAST.

How will the data be collected or created?

If the type 1 data is created based on previous research, it will be collected from the sharing platform such as Github or an official release website. If type 1 data is newly

created, it will mostly be developed by a suitable Integrated Development Environment. For MATLAB language base code, MATLAB software will be used. Spyder will be used to develop Python code. While Visual Studio will be used to develop Fortran and C++ code. The type 2 data will directly be collected from the measurement devices. The type 3 data will be created by executing the source code (type 1).

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

The documentation and metadata cover the points below:

- In each source code, the comments will be written in important lines to indicate the target of the specific lines.
- Information on how to use the source code will be given. More specifically, the information that contains how to configure simulation, perform simulation, and post-processing will be given for users to reproduce the results.
- The reference to the source code will be mentioned.
- Open access paper relating to a certain published code can be referred to.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage any ethical issues?

The type 1 and type 2 data might contain code or measurements which may be commercially confidential, and may be shared only under an agreement or not at all. No ethics issues are observed in this project.

How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

The data produced during this project is owned by the host university (and the granting European Commission ???).

The data should be licensed by 'creative commons' or 'ChooseALicense.com' as open source.

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

During the research, the data will be monthly backed up on 1: mobile hard disc 2: work station of the institute.

Part of the type 1 data will be stored online by the GitHub repository during development.

How will you manage access and security?

Access to the GitHub repository is only available for collaborators during code development before it is made publicly available.

Access to the station PC and mobile hard disc is only possible to authorized personals.

The account security suggested by GitHub and the relevant security regulations at the Wind Energy Technology Institute will be followed.

Selection and Preservation

Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

Type 1 and 2 of the data could be stored for long-term use. While the type 3 is not necessary to be retained since it is reproducible. The data could be referred to by future researchers to continue relevant investigations.

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?

The publicly available data should be available on the GitHub repository for a very long time.

The other data is supposed to be preserved for at least 5 years on the University server.

Data Sharing

How will you share the data?

All the open-source data (type 1) should apply for DOIs (Digital Object Identifier). It will be shared by GitHub repositories and assigning DOIs with the data archiving tool Zenodo.

The data should be open to all users who agree with the license.

During the project, the data should be made available according to the progress, it should be available online once the data is publishable.

Type 2 data and type 3 data should not be shared with open-access. The sharing of type 2 data will be discussed later. While it is not necessary to share the type 3 data since it is reproducible based on type 1 data.

Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

For the type 2 data that is measured by devices from a third party, agreement on data sharing should be made specifying the allowed scope of data reuse. All the other data should be shared with only the agreement on the open-source license.

Responsibilities and Resources

Who will be responsible for data management?

The PhD student of this project: Feng Guo is the main responsible for executing, maintaining, and sharing the DMP.

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

No additional resources are required to deliver this plan.